

PRECIPITATION OF ZINC HYDROXIDE WITH ALKALI AND ITS SOLUBILITY IN AQUEOUS AMMONIA

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The product of gradual addition of alkali to a solution of zinc sulphate is first a basic salt accompanied by varying amounts of the hydroxide. When the amount of the alkali reaches the equivalence point, still a little sulphate is formed along with the hydroxide in the precipitate due in all probability to adsorption. Experiments on the solubility of the zinc precipitate in aqueous ammonia indicates the variation of its solubility.

Bonsdorff (*Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1901, 41, 185) and Euler (*Ber.*, 1903, 36, 3400) have noted that the solubility of certain metallic hydroxides in ammonia solutions varies with conditions of precipitation. Dey and Ghosh (this *Journal*, 1947, 24, 181) and Mehrotra and Ghosh (*Proc. Nat. Acad. Sci. India*, 1946, 15, 161) found that the solubility of copper hydroxide depended on the quantity of alkali used for precipitation. Likewise Shaw and Ghosh (this *Journal*, 1950, 27, 679) found similar dependence in the case of nickel hydroxide. It is shown in the present communication that zinc hydroxide exhibits a similar behaviour. It is further shown that the result of adding controlled amounts of alkali to the zinc sulphate solution is a preliminary precipitation of a basic sulphate together with varying amounts of the hydroxide.

EXPERIMENTAL

All reagents were of B. D. H. Analar quality. A stock solution of zinc sulphate was prepared. The zinc was estimated volumetrically by titration with ferrocyanide following the method of Cone and Caddy (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1927, 49, 356) as modified by Kolthoff ("Volumetric Analysis", Vol. II, p 256) and the sulphate gravimetrically, as barium sulphate.

From 50 c. c. samples of the stock solution zinc was precipitated at the room temperature (29.5 ± 0.5) with the desired amount of 0.0987*N*-NaOH (carbonate-free). This precipitate was afterwards thoroughly shaken for half an hour and was filtered off and washed with cold distilled water. The amounts of zinc and sulphate in the filtrate and in the precipitate were estimated separately. The p_H of the solution was measured on duplicate samples without filtering, using buffers of Clark and Lub (Kolthoff and Laitinen, " p_H and Electro-titrations", p.35) in conjunction with suitable indicators.

The results of the p_H measurement and those of Zn and SO_4 estimations are recorded in Table I.

TABLE I

Expt. No.	NaOH added.	% Equiv. of NaOH.	pH of the mixture.	Amount of zinc in		Amount of SO ₄ " in	
				ppt.	filtrate.	ppt.	filtrate.
1.	0 c.c.	0	5.8	0.0000 g.	0.8208 g.	0.0000	1.207
2.	2.85	10.05	5.9	0.1142	0.7084	0.0679	1.106
3.	5.65	19.93	6.0	0.2314	0.5887	0.1107	1.094
4.	8.5	29.97	6.2	0.337	0.4804	0.1547	1.021
5.	11.25	39.63	6.4	0.4512	0.3663	0.2025	1.002
6.	14.1	49.73	6.6	0.5769	0.2402	0.2272	0.9774
7.	16.9	59.61	6.8	0.686	0.1321	0.2782	0.9269
8.	19.75	69.65	7.0	0.7508	0.0682	0.3086	0.8961
9.	21.25	74.94	7.3	0.791	0.0267	0.3398	0.8656
10.	22.75	80.24	8.1	0.820	0.0000	0.3665	0.8381
11.	24.15	85.17	8.7	0.8166	..	0.2669	0.9378
12.	25.4	89.58	9.2	0.8166	..	0.2442	0.9603
13.	26.8	94.52	9.5	0.8200	..	0.1743	1.031
14.	28.35	100.00	9.8	0.8269	..	0.1095	1.095

These observations lead to the following interesting conclusions.

(i) The removal of zinc from solution is complete when about 80% equivalent of alkali is added.

(ii) The amount of sulphate held by the precipitate also increases up to this point, after which it begins to decrease.

(iii) The pH of the solution rises up to this point, when it undergoes an irregular rise.

Thus, it appears that when sodium hydroxide is gradually added to zinc sulphate solution, zinc continuously separates from solution, both in the form of hydroxide and a basic salt. When all the zinc separates out (80% equivalence of alkali), further addition of alkali results in an attack on the basic salt which transforms it into the hydroxide. All the same, a small amount of sulphate is held tenaciously by the hydroxide (Adsorption expts. Nos. 12 to 14).

Solubility of the Zinc Precipitate in Ammonia.—To study this phenomenon, Zn(OH)₂ was made up with water to 250 c. c. in a volumetric flask and shaken for several hours to ensure uniform dispersion. Known volumes of this suspension were then shaken with a known volume of aqueous ammonia of the desired concentration, the volume of ammonia chosen being such as to leave a little undissolved residue. After standing overnight aliquot parts of the clear supernatant liquid were analysed for zinc. The results are shown in Table II.

TABLE II

Amount of zinc (in g.) dissolved in 1000 c. c. of NH_4OH of

Exp. No.	0.25 N.	0.5 N.	0.75 N.	1.00 N.	1.25 N.
	2	3	4	5	6
1.	...	There is no precipitate in this case.			
*2.	...	...	...	...	...
3.	0.2285	...	...	...	...
4.	0.2451	0.449	...	...	...
5.	0.2806	0.5941	0.9154	1.322	...
6.	0.3244	0.6913	1.154	1.714	1.885
7.	0.3256	0.7799	1.331	1.85	2.251
8.	0.3485	0.917	1.486	2.028	2.616
9.	0.4171	1.001	1.576	2.16	2.784
10.	0.4285	1.114	1.674	2.454	2.885
11.	0.3428	1.019	1.535	2.077	2.708
12.	0.2058	0.9199	1.474	1.886	2.603
13.	0.1199	0.8085	1.382	1.806	2.462
14.	0.0857	0.6886	1.307	1.701	2.731

*The blanks indicate that the amount of zinc present was not sufficient to form a saturated solution under the experimental conditions.

It is evident from Table II that the solubility of $\text{Zn}(\text{OH})_2$ in NH_4OH varies. The maximum solubility is exhibited by that sample of the precipitate which is formed when about 80% of alkali required is employed (sample No. 10). As it is, these figures in themselves show no regular sequence, but more data may help to interpret these irregularities. Further work is in progress.

The author wishes to express his deep gratitude to Dr. A. L. Narayan, M. A., D. Sc., F. Inst. P., Principal, for the kind encouragement. The author is indebted to Dr. Bh. S. V. Raghavarao, M. Sc., Ph.D., A. I. C., of the Andhra University, for his keen interest and guidance during the course of the work. His thanks are also due to Sri D. Neelachal Rao, M. Sc., Head of the Department of Chemistry for giving laboratory facilities and encouragement.